

The Evolution of Financial Technology in Banking: A PRISMA-Based Systematic Review of Functions and Emerging Challenges

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Abstract

Background: The adoption of Financial Technology (FinTech) has revolutionised the banking sector through rapid digital transformation. However, current research often focuses narrowly on financial inclusion and technological acceptance, frequently overlooking critical social, managerial, and regulatory perspectives. This gap underscores the necessity for a comprehensive review of existing literature to clarify the evolving roles and challenges of FinTech in banking.

Objective: Utilising the Scopus database, this study provides an analytical synthesis of academic literature concerning the primary functions and systemic challenges of FinTech within the global banking sector.

Methodology: This research employed a qualitative systematic literature review (SLR) design. Scientific publications from the Scopus database spanning 2010–2025 were screened in accordance with the PRISMA protocol, resulting in 73 peer-reviewed publications for final analysis.

Results: The findings indicate that FinTech integration has significantly enhanced service delivery, increased operational efficiency, and accelerated the proliferation of digital payment ecosystems. Despite these advancements, the sector continues to grapple with

complex issues related to risk management, corporate governance, and evolving regulatory frameworks. Notable contributions to this field are concentrated in journals focused on data science, economics, and electrical engineering.

Unique Contribution: This research presents a pioneering, comprehensive literature review that combines bibliometric and content analyses to provide an integrated overview of thematic trends in FinTech and banking. It specifically highlights the under-researched intersection of digital innovation and regulatory compliance.

Conclusion: FinTech adoption is a primary driver of modern banking success, streamlining payments and reducing overheads. Nonetheless, the industry remains burdened by legal and compliance hurdles, particularly in Islamic banking.

Key Recommendation: Future research should expand this SLR by integrating data from both Scopus and Web of Science (WoS). Furthermore, dedicated studies are required to explore FinTech governance within Islamic finance and the ethical implications of digital banking.

Keywords: financial technology, FinTech, banking, systematic literature review, PRISMA.

Introduction

Currently, technology has transformed human activities into various aspects, making them easier and more efficient. Among them, financial technology (FinTech) has made a real contribution to the banking industry (Neuwirth & Tan, 2024). FinTech provides banks with the flexibility to develop innovative digital banking, shape customer experience and service quality, make transactions more efficient, increase user satisfaction, overcome problems that occur in conventional banking, and improve the performance and quality of banking services (Phan et al., 2020). Therefore, in the digital era, FinTech has emerged as a major force significantly impacting traditional banking activities. This business provides alternative solutions that deliver faster, more efficient services to increase productivity, reduce operational costs, and improve banking and financial performance. Fintech innovations have brought about a significant transformation in various financial services provided by traditional banks, including P2P lending, mobile payments and banking, and digital platforms (Yadav et al., 2024). This means that if traditional banks want to maintain their competitive advantage and customer delight, they have to accept FinTech companies.

Even though cutting-edge financial solutions such as electronic cash and crypto have opened up the door for a greater number of users to utilise a larger variety of financial services, still, the biggest percentage of smartphone owners are turning to FinTech as a means of easier transaction services and instant payments (Reddings, 2023). Furthermore, FinTech has been a driving force behind the digital banking transformation and the development of other sectors such as insurance, investments, and payments. Therefore, this research is important for evaluating the literature on FinTech's role and challenges in the banking industry. Thus, the author explains the reasons for conducting this research. First, the use of FinTech in the banking industry continues to increase. Second, the findings by Li et al. (2025) show that bank financial performance metrics are positively

impacted by financial technology, and fintech enhances banks' capacity for innovation. Third, while excessive fintech adoption can lower bank profitability over time and affect other bank development metrics, such as non-interest revenue, fintech does not have a significant short-term impact on bank profitability (Meyer & Okoli, 2023).

Furthermore, the following justifies a review of the role and challenges of financial technology in banking: First, while most research focuses on the competition between fintech and traditional banks, little is known about the optimal model of collaboration between the two in light of the evolving regulatory landscape. Second, research on fintech regulation predominantly focuses on developed countries (EU/US), while the dynamics of regulation in developing countries, including the challenges of dealing with illegal online loans or over-leveraged paylaters, have received less academic attention.

Third, despite numerous studies examining the impact of FinTech on financial system stability, none have examined the vulnerability of traditional banks to shocks from non-bank rivals, such as e-wallets or peer-to-peer lending. This study examines the role of financial technology in the banking industry and the challenges it poses. As a result, the author formulates the problem to address the following research questions:

- RQ1*: What are the trends in research on the role and challenges of financial technology in banking?
- RQ2*: What are the findings from the discussion in the research on the role and challenges of financial technology in banking?
- RQ3*: What are the potential future directions regarding the role and challenges of financial technology in banking?

Methods

This study followed the PRISMA flowchart model by Tenakwah et al. (2023), employing a systematic literature review (SLR) with interpretive content analysis using a modified PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses). Figure 1 shows a thorough flowchart of the search approach.

Data search criteria

We scanned the Scopus database as part of our initial review. The search was carried out on March 15, 2025, and was limited to publications, journals, and the English language. The search terms used were "financial AND technology OR blockchain AND banking OR bank". The authors used keyword filters in the Scopus database based solely on "Title" and "Title, Abstract, and Keywords." Articles published between 1999 and 2025 were filtered to FinTech and banking. The first set of search results from the Scopus database consisted of 120 articles.

Table 1. Data search criteria

Source (query)	Keyword Search	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Scopus (Article Title)	financial technology	AND Limit to article,	OR Conference paper, book/chapter, review, non-journal, non-English

blockchain AND journal, document, and no relevance
 banking OR bank English, to the topic for review

Three search criteria were applied to ensure the quality of the articles and the reliability of the review. After limiting the search to articles, journals, and English-language sources, we applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria proposed by Alimusa et al. (2024). Therefore, from a total of 120 published articles searched from scientific databases, namely Scopus (n = 120), we limited the search based on (article, journal, English language). We found a total of publications (n = 73). We eliminated papers (n = 47) that were unrelated to the review topic during our initial screening. The total number of records in the Scopus database (n = 73) was filtered, and duplicate article records (n = 47) were removed. We examined all 73 final articles published that needed review. The methods and procedures of this study for SLR are depicted in the PRISMA flowchart in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flow diagram of the search strategy

Tools and data analysis

We performed a bibliometric review as the initial step of the SLR. For the bibliometric evaluation, we used the R-biblioshiny tool to identify the 10 journals with the highest impact, track yearly publication trends, and extract essential details from all full-text publications that required review. Software Harzing’s Publish or Perish (PoP) was used to calculate the document citation analysis (see Table 4). In the second stage, a systematic literature review with content analysis was conducted to ensure that the articles addressed

the study’s objectives. The topic, abstract, and key findings from the full-text articles were manually analyzed.

Results and discussion

Descriptive analysis

To answer RQ1, this section presents a description of the dataset to illustrate the publication trend and development of literature related to the topic. Table 2 presents the primary information from the dataset related to the topic in the Scopus database. Published articles related to the role and challenges of FinTech in the banking sector began to be discussed in 1999. Our findings show a significant increase in the annual growth rate (8.33%), total citations (852TC), and international collaborations (20.97%).

Table 2. The main information

Description (metrics)	Result (data)
Publication years (period)	1999 – 2025
Total documents	73
Number of citations	852
Citation Years	26 (1999 – 2023)
Citations per Year	32.77
Average citation per Paper	11.67
Document average age	2.81
<u>h index</u>	14
<u>g index</u>	27
Author keyword	248
Author	213
Sources	64
Authors of single-authored docs	10
International co-authorship	26.03%
Co-author pe doc	3.1
<u>Annual growth rate</u>	8.33%

Figure 2. Annual distribution of publications

Figure 2 presents the annual publication growth. Although the literature on the role of financial technology in the banking sector began in 1999. Furthermore, the adoption of fintech in the banking sector continues to grow, especially after the global crisis in 2008. Furthermore, Table 3 presents the most popular journals on this topic. We present the top ten sources based on total publications (TP). *International Journal of Data and Network Science* (3 TP), followed by *Cogent Economics and Finance* (2 TP) and Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (2 TP), are the top journals based on TP and TC. Figure 3 shows that all four journals fall into the cluster of results based on Bradford's law.

Table 3. Top 10 journal sources title

No.	Source Title	TP	%	TC	C/P	H	G
1	<i>International journal of data and network science</i>	3	4,11	15	5	2	3
2	<i>Cogent economics and finance</i>	2	2,74	21	10.5	1	2
3	<i>Indonesian journal of electrical engineering and computer science</i>	2	2,74	8	4	1	2
4	<i>International review of economics and finance</i>	2	2,74	3	1.5	1	1
5	<i>Investment management and financial innovations</i>	2	2,74	2	1	1	1
6	<i>Journal of infrastructure, policy and development</i>	2	2,74	1	0.5	1	1
7	<i>Journal of risk and financial management</i>	2	2,74	18	9	2	2
8	<i>Risks</i>	2	2,74	24	12	2	2
9	<i>Applied economics</i>	1	1,37	1	1	1	1
10	<i>Asian economic and financial review</i>	1	1,37	10	10	1	1

Note(s): TP=total of publications; TC=total citations; C/P=average citations per publication; and h=h-index; g=g-index

Figure 3. Bradford’s law (journal rank)

Table 4 presents the most-cited documents related to the Role of financial technology and the challenges in the banking sector. Phan et al. (2020) is the most cited document on this topic (127 TC). Followed Broby (2021) with total quotes (79 TC), which discusses the role of financial technology in changing bank performance, making customer trust the primary concern for banks in providing digital services. Furthermore, the document that is also widely cited is Kumari and Devi (2022) , with a total of citations (55 TC), exploring the development of fintech and blockchain, transforming the banking services sector towards digitalisation. Thus, research on the role of financial technology in the banking sector continues to increase. This indicates that FinTech is raising banks' customer service expectations worldwide.

Table 4. Top ten cited documents

Author(s)	Title	TC	C/Y	Year	Source
Phan et al. (2020)	Do financial technology firms influence bank performance?	214	42.80	2020	<i>Pacific Basin Finance Journal</i>
Broby (2021)	Financial technology and the future of banking	79	19.75	2021	<i>Financial Innovation Technology</i>
Kumari and Devi (2022)	The Impact of FinTech and Blockchain Technologies on Banking and Financial Services	55	18.33	2022	<i>Innovation Management Review</i>
Cho and Chen (2021)	The impact of financial technology on China's banking industry: An application of the metafrontier cost Malmquist productivity index	47	11.75	2021	<i>North American Journal of Economics and Finance</i>
Yударuddin (2023)	Financial technology and performance in Islamic and conventional banks	44	22.50	2023	<i>Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research</i>
Chhaidar et al. (2023)	The Effect of Financial Technology Investment Level on European Banks’ Profitability	33	17.00	2023	<i>Journal of the Knowledge Economy</i>
Zhang et al., (2023)	Regional financial technology and shadow banking activities of non-financial firms: Evidence from China	29	145.0	2023	<i>Journal of Asian Economics</i>
Lee and Lee (2000)	Haven't adopted electronic financial services yet? The acceptance and diffusion of electronic banking technologies	28	11.2	2000	<i>Journal of Financial Counseling and Planning</i>
Alsmadi et al., (2023)	Banking Services Transformation and Financial Technology Role	22	11.00	2023	<i>Information Sciences Letters</i>
Almulla and Aljughaiman, (2021)	Does financial technology matter? Evidence from an alternative banking system	21	5.25	2021	<i>Cogent Economics and Finance</i>

Content analysis and discussion

The Role of FinTech in the Banking Sector

The development of FinTech companies over time enhances banks' financial stability, though this varies across banks. Fintech offers benefits to customers, and banks must enhance their IT arrangements to effectively implement financial technology (Chouhan et al., 2023). The banking industry has undergone a radical change, becoming more efficient, accessible, and user-friendly thanks to FinTech innovations. FinTech has the power to bypass conventional banking, thereby opening the door to a rapid transformation of the sector; the future of banking is already largely technology-driven. However, the essential functions of banking (liquidity transformation and risk management) are still very important. The rapid development of information technology, internet connectivity, and smartphones has driven digitalisation in the banking and financial sectors. FinTech and blockchain are two key technologies transforming traditional banking services.

The combination of finance and technology offers innovations such as digital payments, peer-to-peer (P2P) lending, and investment platforms. This is in line with the findings by Cho and Chen (2021) said that the development of Fintech has contributed positively to increasing the productivity of Chinese banking and that the role of Fintech greatly influences the level of bank productivity. FinTech generally has a negative impact on bank performance, but collaboration with FinTech can improve Islamic banks' performance, particularly in P2P lending. Thus, research on the role of financial technology in the Islamic banking sector continues to increase. Digital technology has enabled Islamic banks to gain new capabilities while reducing operational costs and improving service quality and efficiency. Islamic banks must leverage Fintech alongside marketing strategies that offer value and efficient services, ensuring all transactions are secure, transparent, and free from *riba* (interest).

The integration of FinTech and Islamic finance offers significant opportunities for financial inclusion, efficiency, and innovation, but requires careful management to ensure Sharia compliance and security. Chhaidar et al. (2023) found that FinTech has a positive and significant relationship with bank profitability, making large banks benefit from such investments. Consumers are more likely to adopt e-banking if they see its benefits (e.g., saving time) and increase their adoption intention (Lee & Lee, 2000), and offline consumer behaviours during transactions hinder the adoption of electronic financial services. Hence, offering banks a framework to create facilities that enable consumers to utilise Internet banking for their financial transactions. This study will significantly benefit the banking sector by enhancing online services and revising policies to better accommodate consumer expectations.

Consequently, among the functions of FinTech in the banking sector, the first is to provide access to financial services for those who have not been served by the traditional banking system, particularly in rural or isolated regions. It is important to note that the introduction of fintech in agriculture has brought significant benefits, such as enhanced productivity, a guaranteed food supply, and increased economic strength in rural areas. Next, FinTech has made the use of online payment platforms, digital wallets, and mobile apps to facilitate transactions that are faster, more secure, and more convenient (Yadav et al., 2024). Furthermore, FinTech helps with financial management through tools such as budgeting, investing, and analysing one's financial situation.

Fintech challenges in the banking sector

The primary problem with bringing FinTech into the banking industry is that each country has its own rules to follow. The finance sector's continuous reliance on FinTech has not eliminated some traditional banks' problems with FinTech integration, where continuously changing regulations, such as financial regulation, consumer protection, supervision, and financial stability, among others, have been a hard nut to crack (Barroso & Laborda, 2022). Digital transformation has indeed been the driving force behind FinTech projects, which are already regarded as remarkable developments in the finance sector.

Such results highlight the regulatory limitations that constrain the use of FinTech in the banking sector, particularly in developing nations. One such barrier is the sector's challenge with noncomprehensive regulations. One of the most important global regulations central banks will have to address concerns the incorporation of technological innovations into financial transaction systems. In fact, fintech is sometimes ahead in its development compared to existing policies and regulations (Ahiabenu, 2022). Second, Risk Management and Financial Stability, the rapid growth of Fintech can pose systemic risks if not properly regulated. Unregulated FinTech may jeopardise the stability of the financial system. Third, Adherence to Current Regulations. FinTech firms are required to adhere to current banking regulations, which encompass capital requirements, Anti-Money Laundering (AML) regulations, and Countering the Financing of Terrorism (CFT) regulations. FinTech firms may lack the resources to comply with rigorous regulatory standards.

Fourth, the Regulatory Sandbox and Innovation enable the utilisation of technology to enhance compliance, permitting regulators and firms to test new technologies without the immediate obligation to adhere to all existing regulations (Neuwirth & Tan, 2024). Fifth, Regulators need to collaborate with the Fintech industry to understand the challenges and opportunities faced. Sixth, Regulatory technology (Regtech) requires regulators to adopt new technology to monitor and supervise FinTech more effectively, through coordination between various regulatory institutions in implementing Regtech. Seventh, Regulatory Infrastructure has limitations. In many developing countries, regulatory infrastructure such as payment systems, digital identification, and credit systems is often inadequate. This hinders the adoption of fintech due to the lack of infrastructure support.

Future research directions.

This study summarises potential future research directions (RQ3). We present some gaps in the literature with greater originality, and we explore recommendations for future research. The development of fintech continues to increase, especially in the financial sector, so it is necessary for regulatory strength and rules from policymakers to supervise, monitor, and control risk levels. Future research will focus on developing regulations for technology use in the banking sector, as well as on the roles of regulatory bodies and technological innovation in addressing the challenges of technology regulation. As recommended by Al-Amro et al. (2025), It is necessary to activate financial technology procedures within the legal framework through legislation, and policymakers should prioritise developing supportive regulatory frameworks to encourage the integration of FinTech, especially among small banks. Further research can examine the approach to customer behavioural risk management and the sustainability of fintech investments.

Conclusion and recommendation

Based on a systematic review of studies, it can be concluded that the role of technology in the banking sector has increased since the 2008 crisis. The role of fintech in the banking sector continues to grow because its adoption can improve bank performance, reduce operational costs, increase profitability, provide unlimited customer service, and facilitate transactions. Fintech also provides facilities such as faster payments, credit technology, and e-money. The banking industry's transformation through FinTech has been majorly characterized by the use of digital means to improve banking services, thus making them available to the underbanked population, the introduction of new security measures for transactions along with lowering of the costs incurred in the process, the establishing of flexible regulatory frameworks, the opening up of avenues for collaboration between the legacy banks and the fintech start-ups through open banking, and the analyzing and predicting of risks by means of big data and machine learning. In short, the fintech trend has had a strong impact on the banking sector, serving as a source of innovation, efficiency, and financial inclusion. FinTech also plays a role in reducing costs, improving services, and speeding up the administrative processes.

The results entail managerial implications for governments, banks, and customers. Beyond the opportunities, implementing FinTech remains a challenge for all stakeholders, including banks and customers. Regulation and government support in this sector should be more robust and better when assessing the impact of new implementations on the business and the economy. If we are talking about financial institutions, conventional banks should adopt a dual approach, combining FinTech partnerships through open banking with their own development efforts, such as expanding branch networks, building customer trust, and so forth.

Limitation

This paper has some drawbacks in its research methodology. On the one hand, it offers a comprehensive view of the available literature on the functions and obstacles of fintech in banks, as per the Scopus database; on the other hand, it does not represent the entire scientific literature of the WoS and Google Scholar databases. Hence, it would be wise and appropriate for future researchers to either conduct bibliometric studies using the mentioned databases or carry out a systematic literature review (SLR) on the nexus between fintech and banking performance by combining Scopus and WoS.

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Declarations

AI Use Statement: During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI) for language editing and readability improvements. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the final content.

Data Availability Statement : The data used in this study are derived from previously published articles, which are publicly accessible. No new data were generated; therefore, data sharing is not applicable.

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Authors' Contributions: J.F.F. conceived and designed the study, performed the data collection, analysed the data, and wrote the manuscript. I.U. contributed to supervision, conceptual guidance, and served as the corresponding author. F.T.W. contributed to manuscript editing. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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